

Spectrophotometric Studies on Metal Chelates. Part II. Aluminium Sulphosalicylate

R. K. Nanda and S. Aditya

Instability constants of aluminium-sulphosalicylate complex at pH 2.4, 3.0, and 4.0 at the ionic strength 0.2, determined by spectrophotometry in the ultraviolet region, are $2.48(\pm 0.05) \times 10^{-3}$, $5.37(\pm 0.11) \times 10^{-4}$, and $5.94(\pm 0.14) \times 10^{-5}$, respectively, at $28^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The constants have also been determined at three other ionic strengths, namely, 0.02, 0.05, and 0.1. The value at pH 2.4 agrees with that reported by us by indirect spectrophotometric (displacement) method¹. That at pH 4.0, which is found to be different from that reported by Lasater and Anderson² who used sulphates, has been substantiated by displacement method using copper perchlorate. Instability constants at different pH's can be correlated on the basis of the equilibrium:

From the temperature coefficient of the equilibrium constant, ΔH and ΔS are found to be 5.17 (± 0.2) kcal. and 33.9 (± 2) e.u. respectively.

In the previous communication¹, we reported the results of our investigation on the nature of aluminium (III)-sulphosalicylate complex at pH 2.4, using ferric sulphosalicylate complex as an 'indicator'.

Sulphosalicylic acid absorbs strongly in the ultraviolet with an absorption maximum at 300 m μ , whereas $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ is transparent around this wave length. The addition of $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ shifts the absorption maximum of sulphosalicylic acid at 300 m μ to a longer wave length, indicating complex formation between Al^{3+} ion and sulphosalicylic acid. Spectrophotometry in the ultraviolet therefore has been used as a direct method for determining the instability constant of the complex.

To start with, aluminium-sulphosalicylic acid system was investigated at pH 2.4 primarily to check our previous results¹. Since Lasater and Anderson² have worked at pH 4.0, a thorough investigation of this system at pH 4.0 by direct spectrophotometry has been undertaken. Results by direct method are also different from those reported by them². In our earlier work, we attributed the difference between our results and those of the above mentioned authors to be due to the fact that they used sulphate. To ascertain this, the instability constant of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ -sulphosalicylate complex at pH 4.0 and that of aluminium-sulphosalicylate at the same pH, using the copper complex as the 'indicator', have been determined, using perchlorates. The results by indirect spectrophotometry using perchlorates agree with those obtained by direct spectrophotometry in the ultraviolet. From the measurements of the instability constants at three different temperatures, ΔH and ΔS have been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aluminium perchlorate was prepared by the method followed by Das and Aditya³. Aluminium content of the stock solution was estimated gravimetrically as oxide.

1. Nanda and Aditya, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 577.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1429.

3. *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 473.

Sulphosalicylic acid was of E. Merck, G. R. quality and the stock solution was estimated by titrating against NaOH, standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate. Sodium perchlorate used to adjust the ionic strength was of B. D. H., L. R. quality.

Cupric perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving E. Merck, extra pure grade cupric carbonate in E. Merck, G. R. quality perchloric acid. The solution was filtered through a G-4 funnel and sufficient perchloric acid was added to it before making up the volume so as to adjust the pH of the stock solution between 2.0 and 3.0. Copper content of the solution was estimated iodometrically.

All stock solutions were prepared and subsequent dilutions were made with double distilled water. Stock solutions were stored in well-stoppered pyrex glass wares.

All measurements of optical densities were made with a Hilger-Watt 'Uvispek' spectrophotometer, model H700/303, using a quartz prism. The slit-width at different wave lengths was adjusted to obtain a uniform band width of less than 5 Å. Matched fused silica cells of 1 cm light path were used. To compensate for any error, due to slight non-matching of the cells, readings were invariably taken by interchanging the cells.

The pH measurements were made with a Marconi battery-operated pH-meter, model T. F. 511D. The potassium chloride in the saturated calomel was replaced by sodium chloride. The performance was checked with standard buffers before use.

Solutions for the optical density measurements were prepared and their pH's and ionic strengths were adjusted in the same way as reported in our earlier communications.

The absorption curves of aluminium perchlorate-sulphosalicylic acid mixture were run over a range of pH's. The curves vary with pH in the same way as was observed in the case of aluminium salicylate³.

Molecular Composition

The molecular composition of the complex at pH 2.4 was determined by Job's method of continued variation from the optical density measurements at 310 and 320 μ . at total molarity of 2.0×10^{-4} and 3.0×10^{-4} . The plots of \bar{D} against mole fraction of Al^{3+} is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The maxima in \bar{D} occur at 0.5 in both the cases, indicating that the species formed is the 1:1 complex.

The composition at pH 4.0 was also studied by Job's method at total molarity of 2.0×10^{-4} and 3.0×10^{-4} at wave lengths 290, 310, and 320 μ . The plots are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The maxima of the \bar{D} indicate the same 1:1 complex. No Job's curve was drawn from pH 3.0. Since the composition of the complex is 1:1 at pH 2.4 as well as 4.0, it can be safely assumed that the complex is of the same type at pH 3.0.

The extinction coefficient of the complex was calculated from the optical density of the mixtures of aluminium perchlorate and sulphosalicylic acid in which the metal ion was 30 to 40 fold excess, so that the concentration of the complex could be taken to be equal to that of the ligand. The extinction coefficients of the complex and the ligand at different pH's are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

pH.	ϵ of sulphosalicylic acid at			ϵ of Al-sulphosalicylate at		
	310 m μ .	315 m μ .	320 m μ .	310 m μ .	315 m μ .	320 m μ .
2.4	..	1635 (± 5)	932 (± 3)	..	3438 (± 7)	2633 (± 4)
3.0	2096 (± 4)	3883 (± 7)
4.0	1781 (± 6)	1069 (± 5)	563 (± 3)	4058 (± 4)	3939 (± 8)	3279 (± 6)

The equilibrium constants were calculated in the same way as previously reported². As a check, equilibrium constants were calculated from measurements at two different wave lengths. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Temp. = 28° \pm 0.5°.

Ionic strength.	λ .	pH.	*No. of readings.	Av. values of instability const.
0.02	320m μ	2.4	10	7.34 (± 0.14) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.05	"	"	10	1.23 (± 0.03) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.10	"	"	10	1.88 (± 0.04) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.20	"	"	10	2.48 (± 0.05) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.02	315	"	7	8.12 (± 0.66) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.05	"	"	8	1.56 (± 0.11) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.10	"	"	8	1.94 (± 0.18) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.20	"	"	8	2.52 (± 0.28) $\times 10^{-3}$
0.05	310	3.0	10	2.29 (± 0.12) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.10	"	"	10	3.80 (± 0.10) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.20	"	"	9	5.37 (± 0.11) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.02	310	4.0	10	1.42 (± 0.07) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.05	"	"	10	2.63 (± 0.12) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.10	"	"	10	4.02 (± 0.11) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.20	"	"	10	5.94 (± 0.14) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.02	315	"	8	1.38 (± 0.09) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.05	"	"	8	2.52 (± 0.16) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.10	"	"	8	4.21 (± 0.15) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.20	"	"	6	5.78 (± 0.2) $\times 10^{-5}$

* Taken with varying conc. of the reactants.

Instability Constant by Displacement Method

The optical densities of solutions at pH 4.0 containing $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and sulphosalicylic acid mixture and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, sulphosalicylic acid, $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, and NaClO_4 were measured. From the optical densities of the solutions, the instability constants of aluminium sulphosalicylate complex was calculated in the following manner.

The optical density of the solution, D , is given by

$$D = \epsilon_1[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{free}} + \epsilon_2\{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{free}}\}$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the extinction coefficients of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and the copper complex. Since ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , and $(\text{Cu}^{2+})_{\text{total}}$ are known, $(\text{Cu}^{2+})_{\text{free}}$ can be calculated. If the equilibrium constant of CuR is known, free sulphosalicylic acid concentration can be calculated. Again,

$$[\text{AlR}] = [\text{SSA}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{SSA}]_{\text{free}} - [\text{CuR}]$$

and

$$[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{free}} = [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{AlR}]$$

FIG. 3
 Total molarity = 2.0×10^{-4} ; $\text{pH} = 4.0$.
 In Curves I-III $\lambda = 320, 310,$ and
 $290 \text{ m}\mu$ respectively.

FIG. 4

Having had the concentrations of all the species, the instability constant of aluminium-sulphosalicylate was calculated. At pH 4.0 and at 750 μ , the average values of the extinction coefficients of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and the copper complex were found to be 9.91 and 36.47 respectively. The instability constants of the copper and the aluminium complex are shown in Tables IV and V.

TABLE III

pH=3.0. $\lambda = 310 \mu$.

Temp.	Ionic strength.	No. of readings.	Av. value of the instability const.
15°	0.05	8	$3.21 (\pm 0.18) \times 10^{-4}$
28°	"	10	$2.29 (\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-4}$
40°	"	8	$1.56 (\pm 0.01) \times 10^{-4}$
15°	0.10	5	$5.96 (\pm 0.57) \times 10^{-4}$
28°	"	10	$3.89 (\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-4}$
40°	"	5	$2.93 (\pm 0.11) \times 10^{-4}$

TABLE IV

 $\lambda = 750 \mu$.

pH = 4.0.

Temp. = 34°.

Total concentration.		O.D.	Instability const.
$\text{Cu}^{2+} \times 10^2 M.$	S.S.A. $\times 10^2 M.$		
2.00	2.0	0.409	9.36×10^{-3}
2.50	2.4	0.599	9.58
1.75	1.7	0.305	9.49
1.50	1.5	0.335	8.95
2.50	2.0	0.551	10.20
2.00	1.5	0.426	8.56

Av. 9.35 \pm (0.44)

TABLE V

pH = 4.0.

 $\lambda = 750 \mu$.

Temp. = 34°.

Total concentration.			O.D.	Instability const.
$\text{Cu}^{2+} \times 10^2 M.$	S.S.A. $\times 10^2 M.$	$\text{Al}^{3+} \times 10^2 M.$		
2.00	2.0	2.00	0.230	6.12×10^{-5}
2.50	2.4	2.50	0.279	5.23
1.75	1.7	1.75	0.197	6.05
1.50	1.5	1.50	0.169	4.83
2.50	2.0	2.00	0.285	6.10
2.00	1.5	1.50	0.225	5.33

Av. 5.60 \pm (0.5)

At pH 3.0, the instability constants in media with ionic strengths 0.05 and 0.1 were determined at three different temperatures. The results are recorded in Table III. From these the ΔH for the reaction:

has been determined by graphical method. In Fig. 5, the logarithm of the instability constants at the ionic strengths 0.05 and 0.1 (curves I & II) have been plotted against $1/T$. From the slopes of the linear plots, thus obtained, ΔH has been found to be -5.17 kcal. and -5.08 kcal. for the ionic strengths 0.05 and 0.1 respectively. ΔH was determined at two ionic strengths with a view to determining ΔH° , the enthalpy change at zero ionic strength. ΔH° 's at both the ionic strengths are equal; possibly with the present experimental accuracy ΔH° cannot be determined. It may be mentioned that ΔH of the reaction can also be calculated with the help of the least square equation:

FIG. 5

$$a = \frac{(\sum x_i)(\sum y_i) - (n)(\sum x_i y_i)}{(\sum x_i)^2 - (n)(\sum x_i^2)}$$

where 'a' stands for the slope, i.e. $-\Delta H/2.303 R$.

In the above equation ' x_i ' stands for the arbitrarily controlled variable, $1/T$ and ' y_i ' for the dependent variable, that is, $\log K$ and ' n ' for the number of pairs of observations, which is 3 in this case. The values of ΔH , so calculated, are found to be $-5.158 (\pm 0.201)$ and $-5.076 (\pm 0.13)$, respectively, at the ionic strengths 0.05 and 0.1. The agreement between the numerically calculated values and those obtained by the graphical method is quite good.

ΔF 's at the three temperatures and then, assuming that ΔH does not change with temperature, ΔS have been calculated. The results obtained at pH 3.0 and ionic strength 0.05 are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Temp.	ΔF (kcal.).	ΔH (kcal.).	ΔS (e.u.).
15°	-4.604	5.170(±0.2)	33.9
28°	-5.014	"	33.8
40°	-5.453	"	33.9

DISCUSSION

In Table II, we find the instability constants of aluminium-sulphosalicylate at pH 2.4. The agreement between the two sets of values at the two wave lengths is fairly good.

In either case, the instability constants are found to increase with ionic strength. At the highest ionic strength 0.2, the agreement between the instability constants, obtained by the present determination (2.48×10^{-3}) and that by the displacement method (2.58×10^{-3}), is good. At other ionic strengths, the difference becomes less when ionic strength in case of the displacement method is corrected by taking ions other than those obtained from NaClO_4 into account.

At pH 4.0, the instability constants (recorded in Table II) of the complex have been determined at four different ionic strengths from measurements at 310 μ and 315 μ .[†] The agreement between the values obtained at the two wave lengths is fairly good at each of the four ionic strengths. Besides, as at pH 2.4, the instability constant is found to increase with ionic strength. Lasater and Anderson² found the instability constants of the complex to be 5×10^{-4} at pH 4.0. They did not reported the ionic strength at which they worked. The difference between their values and our present value, determined by direct spectrophotometric method, is too large. Table V shows the instability constant of aluminium-sulphosalicylate complex at pH 4.0 by the displacement method, using copper perchlorate. The average value of the equilibrium constant is $5.61 (\pm 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ which is in fair agreement with $5.93 (\pm 0.14) \times 10^{-3}$, the value determined by direct spectrophotometry in the ultraviolet region.

We have here instability constants of aluminium complex at three different pH's. On correlation we find that incorporation of the hydrogen-ion concentration with a power of unity provides a fairly constant value. So the equilibrium may be presented as

ΔH for the species AlR is 5.17 (± 0.2) kcal. and $\Delta S + 33.9 (\pm 2)$ e.u. The stability of the complex is mainly due to the contribution from the change in entropy. Similar observations have been made in the case of sulphosalicylate complex of iron.

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9

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AND
CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK-3.